

WORKING RIGHT: THE ATMOSPHERES PEOPLE ENDEAVOR TO CREATE IN THEIR WORKSPACES.

Sally Augustin

Principal, Design With Science
sallyaugustin@designwithscience.com

ABSTRACT

Environmental psychology research has shown that people's psychological well-being is enhanced when they personalize their workspaces and has also identified patterns in those personalizations, but it has not addressed the atmosphere people endeavor to create in their offices. Identifying desired atmospheres has practical value, because workspace design can facilitate the development of these intended psychological experiences. The research reported here explored the issue of atmosphere by content analyzing open-ended responses to inquiries about it posed to 259 employed people living in the United States, interviewed during a 10 year period (2000-2010). Across all population segments studied, the most prevalent atmosphere desired was one that nurtured the owner of the space and the second most frequently desired atmosphere was one that inspired optimal performance by people in the workspace. Relationships between desired atmospheres and factors such as gender, age, rank in organization, and organization type were investigated.

Keywords: atmosphere, workplace, environment, design, content analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Atmosphere is best defined, in the context of this research project, as the psychological experience that people in a space will have. The study reported in this paper probed the atmosphere that individuals endeavor to create in their physical work environments through their modifications of them. Investigating this topic moves discussion of changes

made to workspaces by their users from "what" is customized in a workspace and "why" those particular personalizations occurred to a higher-level review of the strategic design objectives of individual workers who customize their workspaces. Identification of desired atmosphere has implications for effective workplace design. Cultural memes related to place design make it possible to develop physical embodiments of desired atmospheres that are generalizable within a specific national culture (Dawkins, 1989).

DESIRED ATMOSPHERES: WHY THEY MATTER

Developing desired atmospheres can be conceptually differentiated from personalizing a space. Although both involve making modifications to an environment, the former directly addresses the overarching objectives to be achieved through change and is more "strategic" in focus while the latter is more tactical. Personalization-related studies have focused on the introduction of particular objects to an environment and the individual reasons why each was added to a space. Practical experience gained during the new research reported in this paper indicates that discussions of "atmosphere" with study participants involve a broader range of factors than conversations about "personalization." For example, issues such as the rearrangement of office chairs to achieve a particular purpose are more likely to surface during discussions of desired atmospheres developed than conversations about how and why people have personalized their environments.

Personalization is generally defined as modifications individuals or groups make to the world to communicate information about themselves (Sommer, 1974).

When Wells (2000) investigated reasons for office personalization by surveying and interviewing working professionals she found "Over half (56%) of respondents indicated that they personalized their workspace to express their identity and individuality, 30 per cent to improve the feel of the workplace, 16 per cent to express their emotions, 15 per cent to show that the workspace belonged to them, 6 per cent to show their status within the organization, 5 per cent to control their interactions with coworkers, and 3 per cent personalized because everyone else at their workplace did" (page 246). She also learned that men and women personalize for different reasons: "chi-square analyses were performed for each reason of personalization by gender . . . More women than men reported personalizing to express their identities and their individuality . . . to express their emotions . . . and to improve the feel of the workplace . . . However, more men than women reported personalizing their workspace to show their status within the company" (page 246).

An analysis of the psychological drives that underlie personalization indicates that similar forces are germane to the development of desired atmospheres. More specifically, psychologically positive levels of control over the physical environment have been associated with personalization (Sundstrom, 1986) and development of a particular atmosphere also indicates an exercise of personal agency. Control of this sort has been linked to reduction of stress (Evans and Cohen, 1987), for example, which has positive implications for professional performance (Sundstrom, 1986). Exercise of environmental control is directly related to the formation and maintenance of territories, which has been linked with psychological health (Brown, 1987).

At a fundamental level, development of a desired atmosphere and environmental personalization both indicate that an individual is creating a space around themselves that facilitates experiences that they feel

are important (Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton, 1981).

Environmental psychology has effectively established a link between personalization of environments by their users and enhancement of those individuals' psychological situations (Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton, 1981). Researchers have found that individual and group mental states are improved when the environment is perceived to communicate elements of their self-concepts valued by either individuals or groups (Becker, 1982; Belk, 1988; Kamptner, 1991; Dittmar, 1992; Lunt and Livingstone, 1992; Richins, 1994; Marcus, 1995; Nippert-Eng, 1996; Gorowara-Bhat, 2000; Wilson and McKenzie, 2000).

Employees that personalize their workspaces have been found to be more satisfied with their jobs and workspaces as well as to experience higher levels of personal and organizational well-being (Wells, 2000). Wells assessed organizational well-being by investigating "social climate, organizational climate, employee morale, productivity, performance and absenteeism" (page 245). BOSTI also found a positive relationship between office personalization and organizational well-being (1984). Other researchers have identified a link between components of the physical environment and job satisfaction (Sundstrom, 1986). Job satisfaction is an important concept to modern managers because job satisfaction and job performance are positively associated (Cote, 1999). In addition, people seem to have a strong psychological drive to personalize their workspaces (BOSTI, 1984).

The definition of "atmosphere" provided in the first paragraph of this paper indicates that "desired atmospheres" are related at a fundamental level to preferred emotional experiences, which can generally be expected to be positive (Fredrickson, 2001). Isen and Baron provide a generally accepted definition of positive affect, "pleasant feelings induced by commonplace events or circumstances" (1991). Negative affect is usually conceptualized as the reverse situation (Thoresen, Kaplan, Barsky, and Warren, 2003).

Job satisfaction and positive affect have also been linked. A meta-analysis has shown that both trait and state positive affect are positively associated with job satisfaction and that state and trait negative affect are related to lower levels of job satisfaction (Thoresen, Kaplan, Barsky, and Warren, 2003).

Independent of job satisfaction, positive affect is important in workplaces because it has been associated with broadened thinking and improved problem solving, enhanced interactions with others, and higher levels of creativity (Isen, 2001), as well as strategic thinking (Loken, 2006). In addition, positive emotions have been linked to the development of social resources such as human networks and intellectual ones, such as knowledge (Fredrickson and Branigan, 2005).

Environmental factors can encourage particular affective states. Baron found that pleasant smells resulted in behaviors that are consistent with positive affect (1990) and Valdez and Mehrabian identified links between the saturation and brightness of colors viewed and emotional state (1994), for example. Additional research has demonstrated associations between social density, lighting levels, amount of enclosure, and interpersonal distancing and affective state (Isen and Baron, 1991), as further examples.

LEARNING MORE ABOUT DESIRED ATMOSPHERES

The data reported here were collected during discussions with people employed in the United States at various types of organizations. Each participant was asked specifically about the atmosphere they were attempting to create in their workspace, after their “workspace” was defined as the area immediately around the chair assigned to them at facilities owned or rented by their employer and “atmosphere” was defined as in the first paragraph of this paper. In the specific questions relevant to the data being discussed in this paper, interviewees were asked “Have you modified your workspace since you moved into it?” and, if modifications had been made, “What was the atmosphere you were attempting to create with the modifications that you made?” The answers provided were content analyzed to uncover patterns in the material collected.

Individuals doing maintenance work or related support tasks were not eligible to participate in this study. BOSTI has shown that professional workers experience the environment differently than support workers (1984).

Data were collected from 259 employed people living across the United States who were interviewed during a 10 year period (2000-2010). Among the interviewees, 84% were male and 16% female. Of the 253 subjects whose ages could be determined, 16% were under 30, 13% were 30-39 years old, 25% were 40 to 49, 46% were 50 to 64 and 1% were over 65.

Based on their apparent professional responsibilities, as discussed during the interview, individuals were categorized as professional employees (doing a skilled task but supervising few, if any, other people), mid-level employees, and organization leaders (individuals at the highest management levels in their organization and directing the future course of their organization). Twelve percent of those interviewed were professionals, 53% were mid-level managers, and 35% were organization leaders.

The organizations employing the interviewees were also categorized. Small, medium, and large-sized organizations were defined using criteria established by the US Census Bureau (www.census.gov). Small organizations, for the purposes of this research project, were defined as having 20 or fewer employees, medium-size ones from 21 to 99 employees and large organizations 100 or more employees. Service providers were distinguished from other groups because of the importance of client visits to those offices. Interviewees’ organizations were categorized as: small firm (19% of total), medium size firm (17% of total), large size firm (10% of total), small service provider (e.g., consulting or accounting firm) (none in sample), medium service provider (27% of total), large service provider (2% of total), small nonprofit (1% of total), medium/large nonprofit (8% of total), government (6% of total), and independent practitioner (no fellow employees) (11% of total).

The coding scheme for the data collected developed after repeated readings of the information gathered. All of the material provided by the participant about the atmosphere they were attempting to create in their workspace was reflected in the single desired atmosphere coded. The types of atmospheres that interviewees were attempting to create were coded as ones that embody the organization's culture (14% of responses received), ones that are functional for the tasks at hand (10% of total responses), nurture the owner (user) of the space (29% of total responses), calm or otherwise enhance pleasant and relaxed moods (11% of total responses), inspire optimal performance (24% of total responses), remind people of the organization's history (7% of total responses), directly boost income (e.g., because of client response to them) (3% of total responses), and finally, spaces that are stimulating and/or fun (pleasant emotion, energized) (3% of total responses).

References to home and "homelike" spaces were frequently made when pleasant and relaxed desired atmospheres were discussed. This indicates an overlap between individual self-concepts in professional and residential environments, as people can be expected to have different self-concepts in each environment (Erez and Earley, 1993).

When inspiring optimal performances were discussed, the speakers were most often referring to encouraging creative or innovative thought.

Only 1 of the 259 people interviewed had not taken immediate steps to create a desired atmosphere in their workspace. This person, who inherited his small-sized firm from his father, waited "to see" what sorts of modifications he would make to the office that had been his father's that he began to use. Ultimately, he did modify the office. This suggests that those interviewed perceived that they had the agency to effectively develop a desired atmosphere in their workspace.

In the content analysis of the 259 interviews, adjectives used in discussions of the desired atmospheres were noted and compared to the adjectives included in the PANAS (Positive and Negative Affect Scale) (Watson, Clark, and Tellegen,

1988) and the Job Affect Scale (Burke et. al, 1989). Desired atmospheres described using adjectives associated with these scales (e.g., "a space to inspire people to . . .") were assumed to be spaces where participants anticipated that they or other people would have an experience associated with positive affect. Positive affect could thus be directly related to many of the discussions of desired atmospheres through searches for the terms used in these scales in the interview notes and in a majority (72%) of discussions of desired atmospheres when similes of these terms were included in the analyses.

The desired atmospheres for population segments were assessed to better understand how year of interview, age, respondent status in the organization, organization type, or gender were related to desired atmospheres. All chi-square test results were nonsignificant when all coded desired atmospheres and (in completely separate analyses) all age categories, rank categories, organization types, year-of-interview time frame brackets, or genders were included in analyses. When employee rank and desired atmosphere were restricted so that expected cell count value assumptions were supported, with a minimum cell count of 5, a nearly significant chi-square value was obtained. The employee ranks included were mid-level employees and organization leaders and the desired atmospheres were embodying organizational culture, functional, nurturing the owner of the space, generating pleasant relaxed emotions, inspiring optimal performance, and reminding people of an organization's history (Pearson chi square = 8.69, df=5, $p < .112$). Leaders are more likely to desire to embody the organization's culture than would be expected and mid-level employees are less likely to wish to do so than might be expected. The situation is reversed for inspiring optimal performance.

When minimum expected cell count of 1 was accepted, a chi-square test conducted with restricted sets of variables yielded a significant result. In that test, expected count was 3.54. When people under 30, 40-49, and 50-64 are included in the analysis along with the desired atmospheres embody organizational culture, functional, nurture owners of the space, generate pleasant relaxed emotions, and

inspire optimal performance, the Pearson chi-square test is significant (chi-square=18.94, df=8, $p < .015$). Those under 30 are less likely to wish to embody culture than expected while those 40 to 49 are more likely to do so than expected. Those under 30 are more likely to wish to develop a nurturing workspace than expected, while those 40 to 49 are less likely to do so than expected.

USING DESIRED ATMOSPHERES TO ENHANCE WORKSPACES

This study introduced the scientific investigation of atmospheres workers try to create in workspace environments. It thus productively broadens the discussion of modifications that individuals make to their workspaces to holistically include the strategies underlying those changes.

The most frequently desired atmospheres nurture the owners of a space (29% of total responses) or inspire optimal performance (24% of total responses). These findings are readily applicable in work environments. Cultural memes related to place design make it possible to develop physical embodiments of desired atmospheres that are generalizable within a specific national culture (Dawkins, 1989) as all messages conveyed through design are socially constructed through symbolic interaction (Berger and Luckmann, 1967; Blumer, 1969).

A nurturing environment is one that nourishes, sustains, supports, and affirms people in their various roles as human beings. It recognizes individual differences and facilitates movement toward personal objectives. To be nurtured, individuals need to have opportunities to display the vast array of items that they feel communicate key aspects of their identity. This information needs to be readily viewable by other employees as well as by the user of the workspace. A workspace that provides nurturing support needs to be readily re-configurable to meet individuals' psychological and physical needs in role-appropriate task-based situations. This requires consideration of both sensory and more utilitarian components of experience. It must encourage positive interpersonal interaction. Workspace designers need to accept that they will not be the final generative force even on any

optimal spaces that they may create and that nothing they establish will remain static as workspace forms must support flexible use as their users and their responsibilities evolve.

The optimal behaviors that individuals interviewed wished to inspire generally involved creative or innovative thought. Research is accumulating about the sorts of environments in which people are most likely to be creative (Ceylan, Dul, and Aytac, 2008; McCoy and Evans, 2002; Csikszentmihalyi, 1996). These findings, which relate to individual design elements as well as conceptual issues, can be applied to create desired atmospheres.

Analysis of interview data indicated a relationship between desired atmospheres in the workspace and positive affect, which in turn has been linked to superior knowledge worker performance (Isen, 2001). The important influence of positive affect on knowledge worker attitudes and behaviors indicates that employer efforts to support desired workspace atmospheres will be rewarded with improved employee performance and well-being, although experiencing desired atmospheres alone cannot determine that knowledge workers will feel positive affect

Elsbach and Bechky fully review the three primary functions of office design (2007). The specified functions are instrumental, symbolic, and aesthetic. The desired atmospheres identified in the content analysis described in this paper reflect these functions, with the most frequently desired atmospheres effectively relating to all three. Instrumental functions "improve the performance and satisfaction of office workers" (page 82). The functionality related desired atmosphere as well as the desired atmosphere related to directly boosting income neatly dovetail with this office function. The symbolic function of office design involves the use of objects and architectural elements to communicate information about individuals and groups. Embodying culture and reminding people of an organization's history clearly are associated with the symbolic function of the office. Aesthetic functions relate directly to the sensory experiences of being in a space. The two desired atmospheres related to

creating pleasant environments that are, either, energizing or relaxing can be tied to the aesthetic function of office design. Since the resulting moods can be related to performance, as discussed earlier, these two desired atmospheres could also be associated with the instrumental function of office design. Nurturing the owners of a space and inspiring optimal performance cut across all three of these office design functions, which may, in part, explain why they were the most frequently desired workspace atmospheres.

This project utilized a convenience sample of participants, but did succeed in incorporating information from a broad range of employees, geographically dispersed across the United States, and working at a range of different types of organizations, which strengthens and adds credibility to the conclusions reached.

Additional research is needed to support the generalization of the set of desired atmospheres identified through this project to broader applications and to determine if desired atmospheres change as workplace design practices evolve. After a general set of desired atmospheres is developed a written survey or similar instrument should be written to quickly and efficiently collect information about desired atmospheres so that designers can supply the most frequently coveted ones to particular workgroups. Application will undoubtedly be at a group level since facilities managers are unlikely to be willing to abandon their existing practices and supply workstations assembled from a fundamentally different kit-of-parts to each member of a work team, unless required to do so by law. If future research links particular desired atmospheres to certain types of organizations or some other readily identifiable factor, this written diagnostic or similar tool will not be required.

It would be useful to broaden the discussion of workspace atmospheres to include desired atmospheres in group, or jointly owned spaces, and to the entire office level, so that the same organizing concept could be utilized at all three design levels.

Workspace design has important repercussions for not only the psychological state of employees but also for the performance of the organization as a whole. Linking workspace design to emotional experience can make an important contribution to workplace design efforts. Work with desired atmospheres seems to be a route to not only better understand that design-emotion link but to apply lessons learned. Future work with desired atmospheres seems warranted.

REFERENCES

- Baron, R. (1990) Environmentally Induced Positive Affect: Its impact on self-efficacy, task performance, negotiation, and conflict. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, Vol. 20, Issue 5, 368-384
- Becker, F. (1982) *The Successful Office*. Menlo Park, CA: Addison-Wesley.
- Belk, R. W. (1988) Possessions and the Extended Self. *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol.15, Issue 2, 139-168
- Berger, P., Luckmann, T. (1967) *The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*. New York, NY: Penguin.
- Blumer, H. (1969) *Symbolic Interactionism: Perspective and method*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- BOSTI. (1984) *The Impact of Office Environment on Productivity and Quality of Working Life*. Buffalo, NY: Buffalo Organization for Social and Technological Innovation.
- Brown, B. (1989) Territoriality. In D. Stokols, I. Altman (Eds.) *Handbook of Environmental Psychology, Volume 1*. New York, NY: John Wiley and Sons, 505-531
- Burke, M., Brief, A., George, J., Roberson, L., Webster, J. (1989) Measuring Affect at Work: Confirmatory analyses of competing mood structures with conceptual linkage to cortical regulatory systems. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 57, Issue 6, 1091-1102
- Ceylan, C., Dul, J., Aytac, S. (2008) Can the office environment stimulate a manager's creativity? *Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing*, Vol. 18, Issue 6, 589-602
- Cote, S. (1999) Affect and Performance in Organizational Settings. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, Vol. 8, Issue 2, 65-68
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1996) *Creativity: Flow and the psychology of discovery and invention*. New York: Harper Collins.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M., Rochberg-Halton, E. (1981) *The Meaning of Things: Domestic symbols and the self*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Dawkins, R. (1989) *The Selfish Gene, revised edition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Dittmar, H. (1992) *The Social Psychology of Material Possessions: To have is to be*. New York, NY: St. Martin's.
- Elsbach, K., Bechky, B. 2007. It's More Than a Desk: Working smarter through leveraged office design. *California Management Review*, Vol. 49, Issue 2, 80-101
- Erez, M., Earley, P.C. (1993) *Culture, Self-Identity, and Work*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.

- Evans, G., Cohen, S. (1997) Environmental Stress. In D. Stokols, I. Altman (Eds.) *Handbook of Environmental Psychology, Volume 1*. New York, NY: John Wiley and Sons, 571-610
- Fredrickson, B. (2001) The Role of Positive Emotions in Positive Psychology. *American Psychologist*, Vol. 56, Issue 3, 218-226
- Fredrickson, B., Branigan, C. (2005) Positive Emotions Broaden the Scope of Attention and Thought-Action Repertoires. *Cognition and Emotion*, Vol. 19, Issue 3, 313-332
- Gorowara-Bhat, G. (2000) *The Social and Spatial Ecology of Work: A case of a survey research organization*. New York, NY: Kluwer Academic/Plenum.
- Isen, A. (2001) An Influence of Positive Affect on Decision Making in Complex Situations: Theoretical issues with practical implications. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, Vol. 11, Issue 2, 75-85
- Isen, A., Baron, R. (1991) Positive Affect as a Factor in Organizational Behavior. In B. Staw, L. Cummings (Eds.) *Research in Organizational Behavior, Volume 13*. Greenwich, CT: JAI Press, 1-53
- Kamptner, N. L. (1991) Personal Possessions and Their Meanings: A life-span perspective. *Journal of Social Behavior and Personality*, Vol. 6, Issue 6, 209-228
- Loken, B. (2006) Consumer Psychology: Categorization, inferences, affect, and persuasion. In S. Fiske, D. Schacter, C. Zahn-Waxler (Eds.) *Annual Review of Psychology, Volume 57*. Palo Alto, CA: Annual Reviews, 453-485.
- Lunt, P.K., Livingstone, S.M. (1992) *Mass Consumption and Personal Identity: Everyday economic experience*. Philadelphia, PA: Open University Press.
- Marcus, C. C. (1995) *House as a Mirror of Self: Exploring the deeper meaning of home*. Berkeley, CA: Conari.
- McCoy, J., Evans, G. (2002) The potential role of the physical environment in fostering creativity. *Creativity Research Journal*, Vol. 14, Issue 3 & 4, 409-426
- Nippert-Eng, C. (1996) *Home and Work*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Richins, M. L. (1994) Valuing Things: The public and private meanings of possessions. *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 21, Issue 3, 504-521
- Sommer, R. (1974) *Tight Spaces: Hard architecture and how to humanize it*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Sundstrom, E. (1986) *Work Places: The psychology of the physical environment in offices and factories*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Thoresen, C., Kaplan, S., Barsky, A., Warren, C. (2003) The Affective Underpinnings of Job Perceptions and Attitudes: A meta-analytical review and integration. *Psychological Bulletin*, Vol. 129, Issue 6, 914 – 945
- Watson, D., Clark, L., Tellegen, A. (1988) Development and Validation of Brief Measures of Positive and Negative Affect: The PANAS scales. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 54, Issue 6, 1063-1070
- Wells, M. (2000) Office Clutter or Meaningful Personal Displays: The role of office personalization in employee and organizational well-being. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Vol. 20, Issue 3, 239-255
- Wilson, M. A., MacKenzie, N.E. (2000) Social Attributions Based on Domestic Interiors. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Vol. 20, Issue 4, 343-354